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Self-protecting X-ray tubes designed before Albert Bouwers' Metalix tube (1924)

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ABSTRACT:

This article describes the various attempts that were made in the early days of radiology to avoid the use of glass or to limit the solid angle of X-rays emitted from the tube before the introduction of a shielded metal X-ray tube (Metalix D) in 1924. The results are presented into five different classes depending on the type of shielding and the application and are based on a literature study.

INTRODUCTION:

In 1924 Albert Bouwers, who was working at the Philips Research Laboratory since 1920, introduced a unipolar X-ray tube partly made of chrome-iron and partly of glass, called the Metalix A [Fig. 1a]^{1,2} that was improved to the bipolar Metalix D

[Fig. 1b] in 1926. The chrome-iron outside shielded all X-rays, except for a small window that allowed the useful radiation to pass and, therefore, was coined a 'self-protecting tube'. This X-ray tube was such an innovation that, upon presenting it at the Radiological Society of America meeting in 1928, Bouwers was spontaneously honored with the RSNA Gold Medal.³ Although he claims to be the first designer of a self-protecting X-ray tube⁴, the question rises whether he really was the first and, if not, why the other designs are relatively unknown. Our research came up with five different classes of X-ray tubes that were self-protecting although not all of these had been designed with this purpose in mind:

- A. Tubes made of metal designed with the objective to avoid the use of breakable glass.
- B. Tubes made of metal designed with the objective to collimate the X-ray beam for laboratory experiments.
- C. Medical tubes made primarily of lead glass, either for shielding purposes, or because soda glass was hardly available.
- D. Glass tubes with internal shielding devices made of metal.
- E. Medical tubes made, or partially made, of metal designed with the objective of radiation shielding.

X-ray tubes with an external form of shielding have been introduced very early and are not discussed in this article.⁵

1. Class A

The first tube in this class was designed by E.A. Woodward and was published on February 29th 1896.⁶ This tube has a conical aluminum exterior with a thickness of 0.1 inch which is an anode at the same time (electrons impinge on the inside from a cathode that is placed in the center of the thick bottom glass base [Fig. 2]⁷, while the X-rays emit on the outside). The claim is made that this tube enabled taking a radiograph of the hand in 5 seconds.

A few months later, Benjamin Davies (1863-1957), who was working in the famous laboratory of Oliver Lodge, introduced his design.⁸ It consisted of a metal tube with a thin aluminum half sphere at its end which acted as cathode with the anticathode in its center. The X-rays, emitted from the anticathode, were penetrating the cathode [Fig. 3]. Inside the cathode, behind the anticathode, there was a half metal sphere that acted as anode. It was reported that during fluoroscopy, at the distance of 9 meters from the tube, the bones of the hand were still discernible. A peculiar fact was that Davies applied mercury as a vacuum seal and porcelain as a high-tension isolator.

Around 1908, Frederick Alexander Lindemann (1886-1957), known for his lithium-beryllium-borate glass, allowing low-energetic X-rays to pass through, designed a metal X-ray tube as well [Fig. 4]. His design had a simple shape and did not use a transparent anode but a window that was transparent to X-rays.⁹ He obtained a patent on his tube in 1908 and later on sold it to C.H.F. Müller. In the same reference⁹, we also encountered a metal X-ray tube designed by the Italian radiologist Vittorio Maragliano (1878-1944) but were unable to find any further literature about it.

2. Class B

X-ray spectroscopy was the first new application of X-rays which Roentgen himself had not yet described in his publications. There have been a number of researchers who were active in this field and needed X-ray tubes that produced thin collimated X-ray beams to aim at the material to be investigated. The purpose, therefore, was not radiation shielding but collimation. These researchers were Manne Siegbahn (1886-1978)¹⁰ in 1915, Peter Debije (1884-1966) and Paul Scherrer (1890-1969) in 1916, Assar Hadding¹¹ in 1930 and John Shearer (1865-1922) in 1922. In the last design, glass was used as isolating material. Due to lack of a good glass-metal sealing technique, wax was used as a sealing medium. Others used tar for this purpose. It is obvious that these sealing materials could only be used under laboratory conditions but not in X-ray tubes for medical purposes.

3. Class C

In 1902, the first (therapy) tube made of lead glass was designed by Alfred Charles Cossor (1862-1922) of the A.C. Cossor Company. He did not have radiation protection in mind but in England usually all glass items were made of lead glass as soda glass had to be imported from the European mainland. It was obvious that the radiation window had to be made of soda glass. This window was located at the end of a protuberance, and, therefore, the tube was also suitable for endotherapy.¹²

In 1905, Albert C. Geysler, a radiotherapist, who became specialized in permanent removal of undesired hair growth (hypertrichosis) by means of X-ray irradiation, designed a kind of therapy tube using lead glass for its exterior with radiation protection in mind. He named his tube the Cornell-tube¹³ after his university. This tube was then incorporated in an apparatus (Tricho System) which he subsequently rented out to beauty parlors. Although he claimed his tube to be completely safe, in the end he lost both hands to the irradiation that occurred through the lead glass. Removal of hair by means of X-ray irradiation is being considered as one of the major medical X-ray catastrophes.

It is probable that Heinz Bauer (1879-1915) of the company Radiotechnische Werke Heinz Bauer in Berlin had radiation protection in mind when, around 1908, he designed the so-called Gamma-Röhre. This was an ion tube with an exterior made of 3 to 4 mm thick lead glass and a window of 0.1 to 0.15 mm thick soda glass. This tube was incorporated in the catalog of Reiniger, Gebbert & Schall of 1912.¹⁴

Finally, William David Coolidge (1873-1975), well-known for his hot-cathode so-called 'Coolidge tube', designed in 1920 a tube made of lead glass with a window of soda glass. Obviously, this was also a hot-cathode tube. Contrary to the previous tubes he placed his tube in an oil bath for extra high-tension shielding. This enabled a more compact tube design.¹⁵

4. Class D

As glass-metal connections were problematic in the first decades of the 20th century, many researchers chose for the option to place a metal radiation-limiting device inside of the glass X-ray tube.

In 1897, Max Levy (1869-1932), owner of an X-ray company in Berlin (Max Levy GmbH für Röntengeräte), was the first to use this option [Fig. 5].¹⁶ He had no radiation shielding in mind, but wanted to limit the primary X-ray beam to reduce the

amount of scattered radiation (the X-ray grid had not been invented yet) and thus avoid the veil of blackening on the film.

In 1898, the Frenchman Victor Chabaud (1860-1922) designed an ion X-ray tube, according to an idea of his colleague Paul Villard (1860-1934), with a conical radiation shield around the anode (both were made of platinum) named “anode à puit” [Fig. 6]. His purpose was to reduce the surface area of the anode producing the X-rays thus suppressing extrafocal radiation.¹ This tube is present in the collection of Zahi N. Hakim (www.earlytubes.com).¹⁷

In 1902 Friedrich Dessauer (1881-1963) [Fig. 7] had the same idea. He did not want to create an internal radiation shielding but to make a tube of which the hardness could be regulated and to use the internal shielding for better focusing of the electron beam on the anode by changing its charge by varying the anode current thus resulting in a better defined focal spot.¹⁸ He also patented this idea.¹⁹ Together with Emil Gundelach, the tube was produced and marketed as the Ideal-Röhre.

In 1915, William David Coolidge got the idea that his hot-cathode tube from 1913 could be supplied with a simple molybdenum hood being placed on the anode [Fig. 8].²⁰ On one side there was a little hole to let the electron beam pass and on the other side a hole to let the radiation pass. Later on, this kind of hood was often integrated with the anode design (‘hooded anode’) to increase the mass of the anode.

5. Class E

In 1914, Ludwig Albert Zehnder (1854-1949) had the idea to make an X-ray tube out of metal. Zehnder was a Swiss physicist who wanted to obtain his PhD at the institute of Hermann von Helmholtz (1821-1894) but due to the lack of a secondary education diploma he was refused in 1887. During a walk in the mountains, he happened to meet W.C. Röntgen. Röntgen was well acquainted with the problems of a missing secondary education diploma and allowed Zehnder to obtain his PhD in his institute in Germany. Thereafter Zehnder became his assistant. In 1890 Zehnder obtained his Habilitation² and in 1893 he became extraordinary professor of physics in Freiburg, just in the period when Röntgen discovered the X-rays. In 1899 he became Röntgen’s assistant for a second time and in 1900 he followed Röntgen to Munich. In 1904, Zehnder became a physics teacher in Berlin where he stayed until the outbreak of the first World War. At that very moment he was on holiday in his homeland and offered his services to the hospital in Zürich, as he had learned a lot about X-ray tubes in the meantime, and, on the occasion of an equipment breakdown, he was able to take action. He realized himself that the X-ray technology would be of help in the treatment of wounded war victims²¹ but he was also disappointed by the fact that the X-rays had caused so many mutilations and radiation martyrs. These were caused by a lack of shielding and by the fact that often the hand was held in the X-rays as test object, to judge the hardness of the tube. He thus got the idea to design a tube with a metal exterior [Fig. 9]²²

William David Coolidge (1873-1975) read Zehnder’s publication and his reaction was: “One could think of many reasons for Zehnder’s tube to be unpractical, but, at least, he has defined the problem in a correct way. Such a metal tube would have great advantages if you could manufacture it at all.”²³ As a result he made an attempt to build a metal X-ray tube himself [Fig. 10] and this, as he found out, was not easy at

¹ This is an idea that Bouwers also applied to his Metalix A tube in 1924 but which did not produce the desired result.

² Habilitation is a German prerequisite to obtain professorship.

all as he was unable to maintain the vacuum even if the tube remained on the vacuum pump. For some unknown reason the metal oxidized. Coolidge, therefore, filled the tube with pure hydrogen and heated it. Then the tube was pumped out and filled again with hydrogen. This cycle was repeated a couple of times and finally the vacuum remained. Another problem was that the glass often cracked in those places where the wire passed through the glass to connect to the cathode. He was able to solve this problem by placement of a metal shield to prevent heating. The experimental version of this tube had a very thin platinum anode such that the radiation was also emitted on the other side as where the electron beam impinged, but Coolidge mentioned that a version with an anode under 45 degrees and a radiation window would also be feasible. He imagined a cone-shaped metal diaphragm around the anode to let the desired radiation pass.

6. Discussion

Zehnder, Coolidge and Bouwers all designed a cylindrical tube (taking up less volume and therefore easier to shield) with an exterior partially made of metal. But where did their designs differ? First of all, the circumstances were different. Zehnder did not have access to a well-equipped laboratory or workshop but worked in a hospital in a neutral country during wartime. Nonetheless he was able to get assistance from the Polytechnic University (ETH) in Zürich. Coolidge and Bouwers did have access to well-equipped laboratories and also had a tube in mind that could be manufactured and marketed. In addition, there is a time difference of ten years between Zehnder and Bouwers and during that time two important developments took place. The first one was the hot cathode invented by Coolidge in a glass tube with a high vacuum. This resulted in the fact that the X-ray intensity (tube current) and the beam quality (high tension) could be regulated independent from one another. Ever since 1913 all tube designs were based on this concept; and Coolidge himself used it in his design as well. Bouwers also applied the hot-cathode concept. Zehnder still used the ion tube principle [Fig. 9]; with a charcoal regenerator, which he had constructed already a month after Röntgen's discover. The second development was the metal-glass connection. This was an invention by Gilles Holst (1886-1968) at Philips, who had noticed that the chrome-iron pipes of the glass blowers would nicely stick to the glass. He obtained the patent in 1922²⁴, and, as a result, Bouwers could make his tube partially of metal and partially of chrome-iron [Fig. 11] and sealed the tube after it had been evacuated. This novelty was not present in the metal tube designed by Coolidge and it was the main reason why Zehnder was not able to take his tube off the vacuum pump. Therefore, it is difficult to imagine how Zehnder envisioned using his tube under war conditions on the battlefield; combined with a vacuum pump? Finally, Zehnder, and we expect Coolidge as well, put the anode on zero potential and the cathode on full negative high tension. Bouwers did the opposite and put, in the Metalix A, the cathode on zero potential and the anode on full positive high tension. However, he discovered quickly that it would be better to isolate both cathode and anode and put them each on half of the high tension (bipolar mode) as subsequently in the Metalix D. If we follow the description by Zehnder²², starting on page 828, we see that Zehnder had to use things that were available such as a porcelain isolator which he had to be connected to the metal part of the X-ray tube by means of sealing wax (this limited the temperature of the tube) while the metal parts were soldered together. The exit window was a convex piece of glass. Zehnder decided not to obtain a patent for his tube design. In January 1915 he went back to Berlin and, on the way, he

visited Röntgen in Munich. While he was there a representative of an X-ray company³, who was interested in his tube, approached him, especially because Zehnder had stated that the output of his tube would be a thousand times larger than that of an ordinary ion tube, which would enable cine-recordings. Max Levy-Dorn²⁶ has uttered his doubts about this statement as Zehnder had not proven it. In addition, he doubted whether the sealing wax was suitable to secure the vacuum. Martinus Eduard Goudsmit (1883-1942)²⁷ believes as well that Zehnder had presented a too rosy picture of his tube, and that he, instead of a thousand-fold output only a ten-fold output had proven. For Röntgen Zehnder had presented his tube design too early and the company representative had the problem that there was no patent. In the end Zehnder's tube was not taken into production and he mentions himself that Philips materialized his idea ten years later.²⁸ In turn, Bouwers was also aware of Zehnder's idea as he refers to it in his publications^{1,2,29} but he considers it as an unpractical solution for special purposes. Bouwers does not mention Coolidge's metal tube, probably because it was not yet taken into production. In his RSNA-lecture in 1928, Bouwers refers to his own tube as "The first, and I may say the best known, self-protecting tube is the Metalix tube".⁴

7. Conclusions

In conclusion we may say that it is curious that Zehnder, in 1914, not had noticed that his colleagues in the field of X-ray spectroscopy, had already tackled the shielding problem. In addition, we can notice that Bouwers found himself in the fortunate position that the chrome iron-glass fusion technique was already available such that he was able to elegantly develop a self-protecting X-ray tube. Although the Siemens-Reiniger-Veifa Multix tube³⁰ came later (1929) on the market, it was known already in 1926 that this would happen. The tubes made of lead glass obviously did not provide sufficient protection and the other tubes were either the result of unique experiments or had a number of disadvantages that prevented them to be produced in large quantities.

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³ This company must have been Reiniger, Gebbert & Schall because they claim that Zehnder granted them the manufacturing of his tube.²⁵ Siemens-Reiniger-Veifa finally put the Multix tube (with an exterior made of porcelain) in the market around 1929 but this tube looked more like Bouwers' tube.

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Figures.

1. The Metalix X-ray tube designed by Bouwers; partly made of metal for radiation shielding and partly made of glass for isolation of the high tension and for melting off the pump connection. 1 = chrome iron middle section of the tube exterior that has been fused to the glass, 2 = copper anode mass, 3 = cathode incandescent tungsten heating wire, 4 = glass part (green) of the tube exterior at the side of the anode, 5 = glass part (green) at the side of the cathode [in the Metalix A there is only one glass tube exterior and are 4 and 5 combined], 6 = anode pastille made of tungsten, 7 = lead radiation shielding, 8 = cap with additional radiation filter, 9 = exterior high tension isolation made of Pertinax (purple), 10 = container for cooling water, 11 = cathode connection, 12 = thin radiation window made of glass (green), 13 = tube hull made of chrome-plated bronze, 14 = supply tube for cooling water to the anode. Fig. 1a. Cross-sectional drawing of the unipolar (cathode is on zero potential) Metalix A (1924) according to Bouwers.³¹ Fig. 1b. Cross-sectional drawing of the bipolar Metalix D (1926) according to Bouwers.²⁹

Fig. 1a: The Metalix
X-ray tube designed
by Bouwers

Fig. 1b. Cross-sectional drawing of the bipolar Metalix D (1926) according to Bouwers

- The metal ion tube designed by E.A. Woodward.⁷ C = cathode, X = aluminum tube exterior which acts as anode at the same time, F = thick glass (green) base plate for electric isolation of the cathode, P = electric connection of the cathode, H = wooden disc to prevent implosion due to the vacuum, E = brass ring connecting the aluminum cone with the glass base plate, D = connection on the aluminum cone for the tube to the vacuum pump, B = tube to the vacuum pump.

- The metal ion tube designed by B. Davies.⁸ The right half of the sphere is the cathode. Inside the left half of the sphere is a hollow metal shield. This is the anode. In the center of the sphere is the anticathode which emits the X-rays that subsequently penetrate the cathode. The high tension isolation is made of porcelain (red-brown) and use is made of mercury vacuum seals (blue). The electric isolation on the outside is made of ebonite (purple).

4. The metal ion tube designed by F.A. Lindemann.⁹ This is a tube with an anode under 45 degrees and a window for the exit of the X-rays. The high tension isolation is made of glass (green).

5. Internal radiation shielding around the anode as designed by M. Levy inside of an ion X-ray tube. The purpose was to limit the X-ray beam in order to reduce the amount of scattered radiation from the patient. The glass is shown in green.

6. The platinum anode radiation shielding designed by P. Villard in the tube of V. Chabaud.¹⁷ Fig. 6a. The ion tube. Fig. 6b. The shielded anode.

6a

6b

7. The special ion X-ray tube, named Ideal-Röhre, that F. Dessauer developed together with the Gundelach Company in order to be able to regulate the hardness of the tube and also to reduce the focal spot. The secondary effect of this design was that the tube was shielded internally.

8. Modification of the Coolidge tube from 1913 with a cap on the anode for radiation shielding. The cap has two holes. 1 = cathode, 2 = incandescent cathode heating wire, 3 = hole that gives access to the electron beam, 4 = cap made of molybdenum, 5 = anode, 6 = hole for exit of the X-ray beam.

9. Cross-sectional drawing of the metal ion tube designed by L. Zehnder.²²
 A = anode connected to zero potential, K = cathode, F X-ray exit window made of glass (green), J isolator made of porcelain (red-brown), M = metal exterior of the tube, V = valve, N = regenerator using C = charcoal, S = siff that prevents the charcoal to enter the tube, B = bottom with a screw thread to change the distance between anode and cathode, R = metal tube that connects the cathode with the negative high tension.

10. Metal hot-cathode tube designed by W.D. Coolidge.²³ a = copper tube exterior, b = thin cone made of platinum; soldered to a by means of silver, c = glass tube (green) for high tension isolation, d = glass inner tube (green), e = copper inner tube, f = hot cathode, g = window made of thin platinum acting as transparent anode, h cathode heating wire connected to e

**Henry Snowden Ward (1865-1911), photographer
& author of the first X-ray textbook:
Practical Radiography (May 1896)**

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Abstract

This article is a biography of H. Snowden Ward, who was a professional photographer, Editor of “The Photogram” magazine, itinerant lecturer in England in 1896 on X-rays, and the author of the world’s first textbook on X-rays “Practical Radiography” which was published in May 1896 and went into three editions with the later editions, 1898 and 1901, expanded and co-authored with Adolph Isenthal, a manufacturer in London of electrical apparatus and X-ray apparatus. Ward was a Fellow of the Royal Photographic Society and a founding member of the Röntgen Society. The descriptions and press opinions of his lecture on the “New Light & New Photography” are perhaps unique, but they are valuable in that they transport us back in time to the very early days of X-rays before medical men took over responsibility for X-ray applications, and the field was organised by photographers and some physicists and electrical engineers. The article concludes with a selected bibliography of Snowden Ward’s books. These include publications about Charles Dickens, Geoffrey Chaucer’s Canterbury Tales and William Shakespeare.

Key words: photography, X-rays, radiography, Henry Snowden Ward, Adolph Isenthal, Alfred Porter, William Morton, *The Photogram*, *Windsor Magazine*, *Strand Magazine*, Röntgen Society, Charles Dickens, William Shakespeare, Geoffrey Chaucer